

BigDataOcean

“Exploiting Oceans of Data for Maritime Applications”

D4.2 BigDataOcean Platform Architecture, Components Design and APIs - v1.00

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Authors: Konstantinos Perakis, Dimitris Miltiadou (UBITECH), Spyros Mouzakitis, Dimitris Papaspyros, Giannis Tsapelas (NTUA), Ioanna Lytra, Fabrizio Orlandi (UBONN), Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis (EXMILE)

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Partners

	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Decision Support Systems Laboratory, DSSLab <u>Co-ordinator</u>	Greece
	Exmile Solutions Limited (EXMILE)	United Kingdom
	Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn (UBONN)	Germany
	Centro de Investigação em Energia REN – State Grid, S.A. – R&D Nester (NESTER)	Portugal
	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)	Greece
	Ubitech Limited (UBITECH)	Cyprus
	Foinikas Shipping Company (FOINIKAS)	Greece
	Istituto Superiore Mario Boella (ISMB)	Italy
	Instituto de Desenvolvimento de Novas Tecnologias (UNINOVA)	Portugal
	Anonymi Naftiliaki Etaireia Kritis (ANEK)	Greece

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Executive Summary

The scope of D4.2 is to document the preliminary efforts undertaken within the context of Tasks T4.3 – Components’ and APIs’ Definition and Design, and T4.4 – BigDataOcean Scalable Architecture Design. Towards this end, the scope of the current deliverable is twofold. On the one hand, D4.2 aims at analysing the technical requirements documented in D4.1 so as to design the concrete components with distinct characteristics and functionalities, properly addressing all requirements identified. On the other hand, D.4.2 aims at designing and documenting the preliminary version of the conceptual architecture of the integrated platform, integrating all identified components into a logical diagram facilitating a complete information flow, which in turn addresses all technical requirements identified and all stakeholders’ needs. The design of the BigDataOcean platform architecture is a living process that will last until M26. Thus, D4.2 constitutes a living document, with updates based upon further identified functional requirements translated into technical requirements, stemming mainly from feedback received by the project’s pilots being merged into future versions of this deliverable, updating and customising or even modifying the architecture accordingly. The current version of D4.2 does not include the actual technical architecture of the BigDataOcean platform, nor does it provide implementation details of each software component or description of the technical interfaces between the platform’s components, since this information is to be included in the future versions.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AIS	Automatic Identification System
API	Application Programming Interface
BDO	BigDataOcean
CSV	Comma-separate values
D	Deliverable
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IoT	Internet of Things
IPsec	Internet Protocol Security
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LinDA	Linked Data and Analytic tools for SMEs
M	Month
RDF	Resource Description Framework
WP	Workpackage
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1 Introduction

1.1 Objective of the deliverable

The scope of D4.2 is to document the preliminary efforts undertaken within the context of Tasks T4.3 – Components' and APIs' Definition and Design, and T4.4 – BigDataOcean Scalable Architecture Design. Towards this end, the scope of the current deliverable is twofold.

On the one hand, D4.2 aims at building upon the user stories of the platform documented in deliverable D4.1, stemming directly from the pilot partners and from the overall analysis of all stakeholders involved, which draw a complete high-level picture of the expected behaviour of the BigDataOcean platform. It also builds upon the elicited technical requirements of the platform, in order to define and document the main components that need to be integrated in the BigDataOcean platform. In this context, the technical requirements documented in D4.1 need to be analysed, so as to design the concrete components with distinct characteristics and functionalities, having in mind that all requirements need to be addressed properly by the components.

On the other hand, D4.2 aims at integrating all identified components into a logical diagram facilitating a complete information flow, in order to design and document the preliminary version of the conceptual architecture of the integrated platform, which in turn addresses all technical requirements identified and all stakeholders' needs. The architecture will be designed in a modular way facilitating easy maintenance, modifiability and extensibility, and can thus be used and easily extended and customised accordingly in order to include further stakeholder's needs not considered until now, including new inputs to reach different needs of current stakeholders, as well as new stakeholders.

It should be noted that the design of the BigDataOcean platform architecture is a living process that will last until M26, and thus D4.2 actually constitutes a living document, with updates based upon further identified functional requirements translated into technical requirements, stemming mainly from feedback received by the project's pilots being merged into future versions of this deliverable, updating and customising or even modifying the architecture accordingly.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

Deliverable 4.2 is organised in five main sections as indicated in the table of contents.

1. The first section introduces the deliverable. It documents the scope of the deliverable and briefly describes how the document is structured. It also documents the positioning of the deliverable in the project, namely the relation of the current deliverable with the other deliverables, and how the knowledge produced in the other deliverables and work-packages served as input to the current deliverable.
2. Following the introductory section, section 2 consolidates the technical requirements already included in deliverable D4.1, which served as the basis for the definition of the platform components and for the design of the conceptual architecture of the platform. Section 2 does not produce new knowledge, but serves for easier reading and easier mapping of requirements to components. Nevertheless, section 2 also serves for prioritising the documented technical requirements (High – Medium – Low), so that different technical requirements are progressively addressed as the project and the platform mature.

3. Section 3 delivers the design of the first version of the BigDataOcean platform architecture. It delivers a schematic providing an overview of the architecture, broken down into a series of components each one undertaking a specific role in the platform operation, and then documents the role of each of those components. The technical components are also mapped to the technical requirements to safeguard that each requirement is addressed by a specific component (or set of components) in the architecture.
4. Section 4 concludes the deliverable. It outlines the main findings of the deliverable which will guide the future research and technological efforts of the consortium.
5. D4.2 also includes two main annexes. Annex I documenting the mapping between the technical requirements and the technical components responsible for addressing them, and Annex II documenting the mapping between the technical components and the technical requirements. These two annexes serve for facilitating easy follow up of the evolution of the user's needs, their translation into technical requirements, and the subsequent modification of the platform architecture.

1.3 Positioning within the project

Deliverable D4.2 is the direct, preliminary outcome of Tasks T4.3 – Components' and APIs' Definition and Design, and T4.4 – BigDataOcean Scalable Architecture Design. D4.2 receives as input mainly the user stories and the technical requirements documented in D4.1, which is the direct outcome of T4.1 – Platform Technology Requirements and Integration Components Analysis and T4.2 – User Stories from Pilots for Big Maritime Data Exploitation, so as to translate them into platform components and so as to design the platform conceptual architecture. Nevertheless, D4.2 also takes into consideration and integrates the documented outcomes of D3.1 – BigDataOcean Linked Data Vocabularies and Metadata Repository Architecture, comprising the direct outcome of Task T3.1 – Big Data Semantic Vocabularies and Metadata Repository, and more specifically integrates the architectural design of the BigDataOcean metadata repository documented in D3.1 in the holistic platform architecture.

2 Technical requirements

The current section consolidates the technical requirements already included in deliverable D4.1, which served as the basis for the definition of the platform components and for the design of the conceptual architecture of the platform. The current section does not produce new knowledge, but serves for easier reading and easier mapping of requirements to components. Nevertheless, further to their documentation, the technical requirements have also been prioritised (High – Medium – Low), so that different technical requirements are progressively addressed as the project and the platform mature.

Table 2-1: BigDataOcean Technology Requirements

Data Value Chain Step	Code	Technology Requirement	Priority
Data Acquisition	DAC-TR-1	The system should be able to connect and acquire data from sensors and IoT devices of different manufactures in real-time or intervals.	Medium
	DAC-TR-2	The system should be able to obtain data from AIS receivers, transponders or base stations.	High
	DAC-TR-3	The system should be able to acquire data from large and popular oceanographic databases including Copernicus through APIs.	High
	DAC-TR-4	The system should be able to upload big data datasets on BigDataOcean infrastructure.	High
	DAC-TR-5	The system should be able to link big data sources to BigDataOcean Infrastructure.	High
Data Analysis	DAN-TR-1	The system should be able to perform big data analytic algorithms on the data stored / linked in the BigDataOcean platform including descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics.	High
	DAN-TR-2	The system should be able to save results of the analyses as datasets that can be further analysed with other algorithms.	High
	DAN-TR-3	The data analysis framework should be performed on a scalable cluster-computing framework, programming entire clusters with implicit data parallelism and fault-tolerance.	High
	DAN-TR-4	The BDO analytics should have the capability to perform streaming analytics.	Medium

Data Curation	DC-TR-1	The system should be able to cleanse the datasets (e.g. remove duplicates, inconsistent values, identify outliers, values with wrong types).	Medium
	DC-TR-2	The system should be able to curate large scale (big data) datasets in a timely and efficient manner.	Medium
	DC-TR-3	The system should be able to store the processes followed for the data curation.	Medium
	DC-TR-4	The system should allow for efficient transformation of data: converting values to other formats, normalising and de-normalising.	Medium
	DC-TR-5	The system should be able to program the semantic curation / reconciliation of datasets.	Medium
	DC-TR-6	The data curation tools can be used offline at the client side.	Medium
Data Storage	DS-TR-1	The system should be able to store and manage large datasets (big data).	High
	DS-TR-2	Setup of different data storage environments should be allowed in parallel in order to accommodate different storage needs (Relational Databases, NoSQL, TripleStores).	High
	DS-TR-3	The system should have high degree of scalability.	High
	DS-TR-4	The system should allow for replication and high availability with no single point of failure.	High
	DS-TR-5	The system should support distributed storage and auto-sharing.	Medium
	DS-TR-6	The system should offer native security and encryption mechanisms.	High
	DS-TR-7	The system should have a direct pipeline with the chosen cluster computing framework and analytics engine.	Medium
Data Usage	DU-TR-1	The system should be able to perform simple and advanced queries over the stored big data.	High
	DU-TR-2	The system should be able to visualise stored and real-time data using common chart types (bar chart, line chart, pie chart, etc.).	High

DU-TR-3	The visualisations should be linked to the queries performed over the data.	High
DU-TR-4	The system should be able to visualise statistics, real-time data and spatial datasets.	High
DU-TR-5	The system should be able to create and save static and dynamic dashboards and reports.	High
DU-TR-6	The system should be able to export data and results of visualisations through APIs.	High

3 Architecture design

3.1 High level architecture description

The high-level architecture of BigDataOcean platform has been designed after carefully analysing all the aforementioned technical requirements. It consists of several interconnected components with specific role in the functionality of the platform as shown in the figure below.

Figure 3-1: BDO High level architecture

At first, data may optionally pass through a data extraction process. This process is performed by an optional component, which for reasons of analysis has been split in three optional components, the Anonymiser, the Cleanser and the Tupler component. The Anonymiser is an optional offline tool that could be offered by the BigDataOcean platform in order to filter the data that need for example to be kept private, such as datasets that include personal information or datasets that include corporate information that cannot be disclosed to third parties. The Cleanser is a second optional offline tool which can be used in case the complete dataset contains noisy and/or erroneous data, and could be used to perform simple and/or more advanced cleansing tasks, for example transformation of data

types, substitution or exclusion of data out of thresholds, or interpolation or extrapolation techniques in the case of missing values. The Tupler is the third optional tool in the data extraction process, and is mainly responsible for the extraction of tuples from the incoming dataset. The Tupler, which could be considered also as an extension of the Anonymiser in its simplest form, should be able to provide a tabular view of the incoming dataset so that only the valuable data for the BigDataOcean stakeholders are kept while the rest of the data that should not be included due to privacy issues or do not offer any direct value in the BigDataOcean value chain are removed. The Tupler should be able to handle incoming datasets in all possible formats like structured data (e.g. XML or JSON), semi-structured data (e.g. CSV files), data originating from databases (relational and NoSQL) and finally data originating for a streaming data source with a predefined data schema. Also, it is possible to upload big datasets directly to the Big Data Storage.

The next component in the foreseen logical flow is the Annotator (Mapper). The main responsibility of the Annotator is to semantically annotate the extracted dataset utilising the ontologies and vocabularies available in the repository. For this purpose, the consortium will provide upper-level ontologies and vocabularies covering the domain-specific needs of BigDataOcean and will make sure that these are available to the Annotator and moreover that they can be extended upon needs in the future. The semantic annotation is the process of enriching the data with well-defined semantics of a domain model. With this annotation, the content of the data is mapped inside the context of the domain and also semantic relationships can be utilised to provide information about the content and its relationship with other content. The purpose is to build a network of data that can be easily interpreted, combined and reused by computers.

Optionally and before the annotated datasets are stored, they are received by the RDF Transformation Engine towards the transformation from semantically enriched data to RDF format. RDF is a W3C recommended standard for representing data and metadata (i.e. description of data like its schema and business-meaning) which can support semantics-aware Business Intelligence. Using a variety of syntax notations and data serialisation formats, semantic meaning of data items is defined so as to be used for the conceptual description and modelling of information. The main concept of RDF is to represent everything in terms of triples, which are basically the data model of RDF which in turn has three components: 1) the Subject (S), 2) the Predicate (P), and 3) the Object (O). RDF Transformation Engine produces those RDF triples based on a list of predefined rules.

Following the optional transformation into RDF, the Big Data Storage encapsulates the storage solution of the BigDataOcean platform. It is where all the large datasets, RDF triples and semantically annotated metadata will reside. As in every existing big data project the storage solution has to offer a set of key characteristics which are crucial for the platform as a whole. Big Data Storage should offer horizontal scalability, high availability and flexibility. It should be capable of storing and managing large amount of possibly unrelated and complex data efficiently. Also, high performance querying and indexing capabilities of the storage solution are included in the set of key characteristics. Big Data Storage should ensure content is widely accessible and highly available by the rest of the components while also it should offer advanced data protection. Finally, the storage solution should offer the capability of uploading large sets in a timely and efficient manner.

In parallel to the data storage, the extracted and semantically enriched data are provided to the Data Indexer. The purpose of the Data Indexer is to provide near real-time indexing and advanced querying capabilities. More specifically, the datasets are stored following a specified structural format in a

persistent storage along with indexes created during processing time in order to be ready for subject indexing.

On the top of the data storage, BigDataOcean will also provide a data management tool capable of supporting maritime data sources harmonisation named Ontario. Ontario will address the problem that the data coming from these sources are stored in various different formats, offering a layer of abstraction over the data with semantification on-the-fly using the BigDataOcean's vocabularies and ontologies. The purpose is to provide a unified query mechanism which will support querying these data as if they were heterogeneous data sources.

The Query Builder comprises the graphical user interface through which the user can create simple or complex queries with an easy (self-explanatory), efficient and friendly way. The user will be able to choose from multiple data sources and several predefined filters in order to easily define the query upon his/her needs. The results of the executed query will be presented with pagination and will be available for further filtering upon selection. Besides the Query Builder's user interface the results will be also provided to the Visualiser as an input.

For each algorithm that requires (or accepts) parameter values as input, the Algorithm Customiser is responsible for collecting the parameter values of the algorithm as selected by the user, and for feeding them to the Algorithm Controller. The Algorithm Controller is the main component responsible for the overall handling of the execution of the algorithm. This mainly includes initiating a request to the Spark framework for the execution and waiting for the results of the execution that will later be provided to the Visualiser.

In addition to the Algorithm Controller and towards the offering of extended analysis capabilities, the Algorithm Combiner will materialise the ability of multiple algorithm execution in a chainable way. More specifically, this component will be responsible to provide the results of an algorithm execution as the input of a subsequent algorithm execution, adding further value on the analysis performed.

The Visualiser is the component responsible for the visualisation of the results of the executed query as composed by the Query Builder, or for the visualisation of the results of the executed analysis by the Algorithm Controller. The Visualiser will offer a variety of data visualisations such as histograms, line graphs, pie charts, heat maps, bar and scatter plots, tables and maps in the form of customisable and flexible dynamic dashboards.

Apache Spark is the cluster-computing framework needed for the data processing part of the BigDataOcean platform. Spark is built with the objective to provide a processing engine focused on performance, speed, reliability and ease of use. It is an open-source project most suitable for analytics. Spark is designed around the concept of a data structure called the resilient distributed dataset (RDD), a read-only multiset of data items distributed over a cluster of machines, that is maintained in a fault-tolerant way. Utilising an easy to use interface it achieves the programming of entire clusters with implicit data parallelism and fault-tolerance. Through the design and usage of the RDDs it offers the opportunity to implement iterative algorithms that run over their datasets multiple times in a loop and also to implement interactive/exploratory data analysis. Moreover, the iterative algorithms are the basis for the machine learning technics used by Spark.

Apache Hadoop YARN is a cluster management technology. YARN has become core part of the latest Hadoop project and it is the architectural centre of it. The reason is that YARN allows multiple data processing engines such as interactive SQL, real-time streaming, data science and batch processing to

handle data stored in a single platform. YARN offers a centralised platform responsible for the resource management and the delivery of consistent operations, data governance tools across Hadoop clusters and overall security. YARN's resource manager is handling effectively distribution of the system resources among the cluster nodes based on the monitoring and reporting functionalities of the node manager agent running on each individual cluster node. YARN's dynamic allocation of cluster resources improves linear-scale storage and processing in a cost-effective way.

3.2 BigDataOcean Components specifications

The current section of the document provides more analytical information per component of the architecture, while mapping the components to the documented technical requirements. An initial sequence diagram (which could be updated in future versions of the deliverable) is also provided to illustrate the perceived information flow and the interaction amongst components, which will in turn facilitate the design of the technical interfaces (APIs) amongst the components.

3.2.1 Anonymiser

The Anonymiser is an offline tool with the purpose of data anonymization. Data anonymization is a very crucial aspect when datasets need to be uploaded or shared on a platform. It is usual that without data anonymization the transfer of information across a boundary, which could be either a company network, an organisation or a personal perspective when sharing personal data, might not be possible or acceptable. The Anonymiser tool must deal with privacy issues, eliminate the risk of unintended disclosure and protect sensitive personal data. It must be able to deal with sensitive attributes in a way the privacy threats like attribute disclosure or identity disclosure are handled properly. Several anonymization techniques like data masking, data encryption or data scrambling will be considered during implementation having in mind that the tool must achieve a balance between data utility and privacy.

The Anonymiser does not meet any specific technical requirements, since it was not deemed a necessity during the stakeholders' needs' analysis to anonymise sensitive information. Nevertheless, the Anonymiser has been included as an optional component, because such a need may arise in the future, and thus the delivery of such a tool may be deemed beneficial for a stakeholder wishing to share a data source through the BDO platform.

The Anonymiser will receive datasets from the data sources in order to offer an effective way of filtering the original data upon the user needs. For this reason, the user will be able to choose and customise the applicable risk models, privacy models, transformation models and data utility measures before the tool will perform the anonymization process. The output of the anonymised datasets will be offered either the optional Cleanser tool or the Tuples component.

Figure 3-2 displays the execution flow of Anonymiser.

Figure 3-2: Anonymiser Sequence Diagram

3.2.2 Cleanser

Cleanser is an additional optional offline tool with the purpose of data cleansing. Data cleansing is the process of detecting and correcting (or removing) corrupt or inaccurate records from a dataset (in the form of record set, table, database, etc.) and refers to identifying incomplete, incorrect, inaccurate or irrelevant parts of the data and then replacing, modifying, or deleting the dirty or coarse data. It is very common also that entries in a dataset are duplicated or partially missing. Any possible inconsistencies are usually originally caused by user entry errors, by corruption in data transmission or during data storage and the differences in the data schema definitions of the various datasets.

The purpose of Cleanser is that the cleansed dataset will be consistent with other similar data sets in the system. The most important quality characteristics to be considered are data integrity, data precision, data accuracy, data reliability. Towards these characteristics there are several techniques that will be applied depending on the detected issue and the desired result. This includes data type transformation, substitution, removal or exclusion of data based on defined thresholds and acceptance models, data completion based on interpolation or extrapolation techniques.

The process of data cleansing starts with data identification and analysis of the content which includes which dataset is selected, where it is stored, in what format and what of type of data it contains. Once the data have been identified and analysed by the tool, selection of the part of the dataset to be cleansed will be offered which includes fields selection, column selection or data type selection and more. Afterwards the user will set the parameters of the cleansing specifications and rules and according to the parameters set, the list of available utilities and actions will be displayed. Finally, the data cleansing execution will take place with the selected tools and the output will be offered to the Tupler component.

The Cleanser will address the following requirements:

1. **DC-TR1:** Cleanser will be able to cleanse the datasets by removing duplicates, correcting corrupted, incomplete or inaccurate records, correcting incomplete or partially missing records.
2. **DC-TR-3:** The Cleanser will be able to store the processes followed for the data cleaning in case they need be applied in similar datasets in the future.
3. **DC-TR6:** Cleanser will be available to be used offline at the client side.

Figure 3-3 displays the execution flow of Cleanser.

Figure 3-3: Cleanser Sequence Diagram

3.2.3 Tupler

The Tupler is a component that contributes to the process of uploading datasets into the BigDataOcean platform. Its main responsibility is the extraction of tuples from the incoming dataset and the creation of a tabular view of them, containing only the desired data to be kept and uploaded.

The Tupler will address the following requirements:

1. **DAC-TR1:** Tupler allows end users to connect and acquire data from sensors and IoT devices of different manufactures in real-time or intervals.
2. **DAC-TR2:** Tupler supports the collection of data from AIS receivers, transponders or base stations.
3. **DAC-TR3:** Data from large and popular oceanographic databases can be fetched using Tupler.

4. **DAC-TR4:** Tupler will be used to upload big data datasets on the BigDataOcean platform.

More specifically, while providing datasets, these may often contain information that is either sensitive, like personal or private information, or it is not considered valuable for the related stakeholders. Therefore, this information has to be removed in order to keep only the desired and valuable data. The Tupler is going to provide to the data providers the functionality to select the specific columns or the attributes that they want to include in the uploaded datasets. The component's input can be either raw data or data that have been anonymised and cleaned from the responsible components. Moreover, the Tupler will be able to receive data in multiple formats, such as data from relational or NoSQL databases, structured data (e.g. XML or JSON), semi-structured (e.g. CSV) or streaming data.

The process that the Tupler executes starts with the user providing a sample of the incoming dataset that he wants to feed into the BigDataOcean platform. Then, depending on the type of the data, there are two alternatives. If the provided data are either structured or semi-structured, then the Tupler is able to extract the data schema and present it to the user. Otherwise, if the data are unstructured (e.g. streaming data), then the user has to provide a predefined schema that describes the data. The next step is the selection from the user's side of the attributes that will be included, based on the presented schema and then, the full dataset is ready to be imported. Finally, the Tupler extracts the tabular view of the dataset based on the user's selection and either sends it to the big data storage, or to the annotator in order to perform the semantic enrichment.

The following figure displays the execution flow of the BDO Tupler.

Figure 3-4: Tupler Sequence Diagram

3.2.4 Metadata Repository

The Metadata Repository will allow users to import, manage, query, and interlink vocabularies related to the maritime domain. It will eventually provide APIs to the Annotator/Mapper for retrieving related ontologies and vocabularies from the repository and mapping them to maritime datasets.

The Metadata Repository will address the following requirements:

1. **DC-TR-4:** The transformation of data (converting values to other formats, normalising and de-normalising) will be possible with the use of ontologies and vocabularies stored in the Metadata Repository
2. **DC-TR-5:** The Metadata Repository will provide the tools for realising the semantic curation and reconciliation of datasets

The following figure contains the main components included in the BigDataOcean Metadata Repository. In particular:

- **Vocabulary Importer:** This component is responsible for importing ontologies and vocabularies of different formats;
- **Metadata Management:** Is responsible for CRUD (Create, Read, Update and Delete) operations regarding all metadata; it also manages the versioning of the vocabularies;
- **Statistics:** It calculates and persists statistics about the vocabulary metadata persisted in the metadata repository;
- **Quality Metrics:** It calculates and persists quality metrics about the vocabulary metadata persisted in the metadata repository;
- **Search / Query Engine:** Provides search and query capabilities on top of the metadata persisted in the metadata repository;
- **UI:** Graphical User Interface for interaction of vocabulary publishers and consumers with the metadata repository.

Figure 3-5: Metadata Repository Architecture

On the bottom level, the vocabulary metadata refers to vocabularies that are published as Linked Open data. The BigDataOcean Metadata Repository provides a SPARQL endpoint and API that can be used as well by other BigDataOcean tools providing Semantic Enrichment, Data Linking, and Data Management.

Figure 3-6: Metadata Repository Sequence Diagram

3.2.5 Annotator / Mapper

The goal of the Annotator (Mapper) is to semantically annotate datasets in input, provided by the Tupler component, utilising metadata vocabularies available in the Metadata Repository. As described in Section 3.2.4, the Metadata Repository contains ontologies/vocabularies for describing both metadata about the datasets themselves and the data contained in these datasets as well. Domain specific vocabularies are used for representing the meaning of the attributes inside each dataset. The component responsible for associating a meaning (or annotating) to each attribute of the datasets is the Annotator.

The Annotator requires the input of domain experts in order to perform the annotation of the data attributes which are being imported into the BDO platform. The domain expert has the role of choosing from the Metadata Repository which terms best match the meaning of the attributes in the dataset.

Some of the annotations can be automated, i.e. they would be done automatically without user input whenever possible. A GUI for the Annotator will allow users to specify the annotations. The annotations are received by the RDF Metadata Transformation Engine which can translate and store these metadata descriptions of the datasets into RDF and eventually (only if needed, depending on the use case) transform the entire dataset into RDF.

The Annotator will address the following requirements:

1. **DAC-TR-5:** The system should be able to link big data sources to BigDataOcean Infrastructure.
2. **DC-TR-3:** The Annotator will be able to store the processes followed for the semantic annotation of datasets in case they need be applied in similar datasets in the future.
3. **DC-TR-5:** The system should be able to program the semantic curation / reconciliation of datasets.
4. **DC-TR-6:** The data curation tools can be used offline at the client side.

The BDO Annotator will build on the existing Transformation Tool developed by the LinDa project. The following four functionalities are already fulfilled by the LinDA Transformation Tool:

1. Transformation of relational datasets (e. g. from SQL databases) into RDF graphs;
2. Transformation of (possibly big) tabular datasets into RDF graphs (e.g. from CSV/Excel datasets);
3. Registration, mapping, querying and recommendation of vocabularies;
4. Publishing newly created Linked Data as Linked Open Data (LOD) or Linked Enterprise Data.

Figure 3-7: LinDA Transformation Tool Architecture

The Transformation Tool consists of the Mapping Designer and the Transformation Engine. A diagram of the Transformation Tool is in Figure 3-7: LinDA Transformation Tool. The Mapping Designer provides all functionality required for designing a transformation mapping (this component would be functionally equivalent to the BDO Mapper). The Transformation Engine is the component in charge of all functionality relating to the actual transformation process from (semi-)structured data sources into semantically enriched RDF (this would be functionally equivalent to the BDO RDF Metadata

Transformation Engine). In BigDataOcean we will reuse these already existing components and improve their functionality if needed.

The following figure illustrates the interaction between the users and the Annotator / Mapper, as well as the communication between the Annotator / Mapper and the RDF Metadata Transformation Engine. In particular, uses the Annotator / Mapper in order to edit mappings between datasets and vocabularies and the Transformation Engine in order to transform datasets given specific mappings, e.g., relational datasets, tabular datasets, etc. In case of data transformation, the RDF Metadata Transformation Engine contacts the Annotator / Mapper in order to retrieve the appropriate mappings for transformation.

Figure 3-8: Annotator / Mapper Sequence Diagram

3.2.6 RDF Metadata Transformation Engine

The RDF Metadata Transformation Engine (RMTE) is used for transforming tabular or relational data to RDF. The underlying motivations for this is to allow for seamless data interlinking and to provide a way towards the creation of Linked Data, even for users who are not necessarily familiar with the core concepts of the Semantic Web. RDF (and Linked Data) is a W3C recommended standard for representing data and metadata which can support semantics-aware Business Intelligence. The RMTE produces those RDF triples based on a list of predefined rules or mappings specifications provided by the Annotator.

Here, the term “transformation” particularly refers to semantic enrichments. Technically, that means that data is formalised by means of types and properties that come from appropriate vocabularies (or ontologies). But such vocabularies need first to be known before they can be used. This explains why the Metadata Repository and the Annotator are essential components connected to the RMTE.

The RDF Metadata Transformation Engine will address the following requirements:

1. **DAC-TR-5:** The system should be able to link big data sources to BigDataOcean Infrastructure.
2. **DC-TR-3:** The RMTE will be able to store the processes followed for the transformation of tabular or relational data to RDF in case they need be applied in similar datasets in the future.
3. **DC-TR-5:** The system should be able to program the semantic curation / reconciliation of datasets.
4. **DC-TR-6:** The data curation tools can be used offline at the client side.

As previously described in Section 3.2.5 for the Annotator, the BDO RMTE will reuse the components already available from the LinDA Project. In particular the LinDA Transformation Tool, depicted in Figure 3-7: LinDA Transformation Tool, allows for (i) RDF transformation of relational datasets (e.g. from SQL databases) and (ii) transformation of (possibly big) tabular datasets (e.g. from CSV/Excel datasets) into RDF graphs. In BigDataOcean we will reuse these existing components and improve their functionality if needed. The interactions between the user and the RDF Metadata Transformation Engine, as well as the interaction with the Annotator / Mapper are depicted in Figure 3-8.

3.2.7 Big Data Framework & Storage

As in any Big Data analytics platform the cluster computing framework and the storage solution hold a dominant role on the platform. The efficiency and success of the platform is highly related on these two components of the system.

The Big Data Framework is the cluster computing framework that offers the processing engine for the analysis along with cluster management and scheduling. The processing engine will be suitable for analysis execution combining speed, performance, reliability and efficiency. It will support clustering with data parallelism and fault-tolerance along with a large variety of analysis algorithms suitable for the BigDataOcean platform goals and purposes. For the purposes of BigDataOcean, Apache Spark has been selected. Spark offers management for the execution of distributed application on a cluster following the master/slave architecture along with a cluster manager. The main idea of Spark is the existence of one master process acting as a central point and entry point with the responsibility to collect usage information from all available nodes of the cluster and afterwards the distribution of specific job to each of the nodes utilising an effective cluster management. To support the execution of job the cluster is dynamically allocating resources accordingly, assigning the nodes with a specific job and monitoring the status of the job along with requests for further resources upon needs. One more key characteristic of Spark is the feature of resilient distributed dataset (RDD) which is a concept of read-only multiset of data items distributed among the nodes of the cluster, enabling data parallelism. To supplement the functionality of Spark, Apache YARN is selected for the role of cluster management. YARN is offering the support of multiple data processing engines enabling Spark with extended functionalities like enhanced resource management, job scheduling and monitor tools over the cluster nodes. Besides that, YARN is implementing security mechanisms missing on the Spark framework. The role of YARN is to increase effectiveness of dynamic allocation of resources, monitoring and resources capabilities. Both Spark and YARN are offering high level APIs and specialised tools for machine learning and graph processing. Big Data Framework will receive requests for analysis and algorithms execution on the multiple datasets selected by the Algorithms Controller and will provide the results of the analysis back to the Algorithms Controller once the analysis is finished.

The Big Data Storage of the BigDataOcean platform is the component responsible for storing the large datasets, RDF triples and semantically annotated metadata. It is a core component of the BigDataOcean platform and tightly coupled with the Big Data Framework. The Big Data Storage will offer a distributed storage which will be able to scale horizontally, with high availability, flexibility and fault-tolerance. It should be highly performant to handle multiple concurrent requests with high performance querying and indexing capabilities. Moreover, it should be able to cope with large amount of unrelated and complex data and be able to scale in an efficient way. Of course, as with every storage solution the Big Data Storage should offer high availability and data security. The Big Data Storage should be able to receive large datasets directly from the data sources or extracted large datasets coming from the Tupler

component, and should also facilitate the storage of the semantically annotated metadata or the semantically annotated RDF triples produced by the Annotator or the RDF Transformation Engine components accordingly.

The Big Data Framework & Storage addresses the following requirements:

1. **DAC-TR-1:** The Big Data Storage is able to connect to (either in a direct manner through custom developed connectors or through the data check in process) and acquire data from sensors and IoT devices of different manufactures in real-time or intervals.
2. **DAC-TR-2:** The Big Data Storage is able to connect to (either in a direct manner through custom developed connectors or through the data check in process) and acquire data from AIS receivers, transponders or base stations.
3. **DAC-TR-3:** The Big Data Storage is able to connect to (either in a direct manner through custom developed connectors or through the data check in process) and acquire data from large and popular oceanographic databases including Copernicus through APIs.
4. **DAC-TR-4:** The Big Data Storage allows uploading big data datasets on the BigDataOcean infrastructure.
5. **DAN-TR-3:** The Big Data Framework & Storage allows the performance of the desired data analytics on a scalable cluster-computing framework, programming entire clusters with implicit data parallelism and fault-tolerance.
6. **DC-TR-2:** The Big Data Storage allows for the curation of large scale (big data) datasets in a timely and efficient manner.
7. **DS-TR-1:** The Big Data Storage facilitates the effective and efficient storage and management of large datasets (big data).
8. **DS-TR-2:** The Big Data Framework & Storage allows the parallel setup and operation of different data storage environments in order to accommodate different storage needs (Relational Databases, NoSQL, TripleStores).
9. **DS-TR-3:** The Big Data Framework & Storage has high degree of scalability.
10. **DS-TR-4:** The Big Data Framework & Storage allows for replication and high availability with no single point of failure.
11. **DS-TR-5:** The Big Data Framework & Storage supports distributed storage and auto-sharing.
12. **DS-TR-7:** The Big Data Storage has a direct pipeline with the chosen cluster computing framework and analytics engine, namely the Big Data Framework.

Figure 3-9 displays the execution flow of Big Data Framework and Big Data Storage.

Figure 3-9: Big Data Framework and Storage Sequence Diagram

3.2.8 BDO Data Indexer

The BDO Data Indexer is the component where the data sources that have been stored on the Big Data Storage, after extraction and transformation from the original data sources, are indexed. The purpose of the Data Indexer is to achieve fast search responses along with advanced search capabilities.

The BDO Data Indexer is designed with the concept of Document and Index in mind. Document is the unit of search and it consists of one or more Fields, while an Index consists of one or more documents. The index is conceptualised as an inverted index because it is based on a keyword-centric data structure. To support this concept, the existence of well-defined schema is important and crucial. The schema declares what kinds of fields exist on the document, which field should be used as the primary key, which fields are required and also how to index and search each field. For BigDataOcean the schema of the Data Indexer will be compiled with references on the BigDataOcean available ontologies. The BDO Data Indexer is composed by two main processes, the Index Schema Manager and the Index Document Creator. The Index Schema Manager is responsible for maintaining the aforementioned schema needed for the correct functionality of the Data Indexer. Also, for every new data source that will be added in the Big Data Storage the Index Schema Manager is responsible for checking the enriched data coming from the Annotator against the established schema and identify possible update of the schema needs. The Index Document Creator is responsible for receiving any new dataset stored on the Big Data Storage along with any metadata (for example Dublin Core metadata) as input with the purpose of indexing these data based on the schema defined.

The purpose of the Data Indexer is support to the Query Builder which should be bound to the Index Schema Manager into an intuitive user-friendly query interface providing functionalities like the following:

- results highlighting,
- spell correction and suggestion,
- terms boosting,
- semantic distance,
- auto complete functionality on users' queries,

- geospatial search,
- load/save queries,
- user access control,
- results exporting to multiple formats (XML, JSON, CSV, binary).

The BDO Data Indexer addresses the following requirements:

1. **DAC-TR-5:** The BDO Data Indexer facilitates the linking of big data sources to BigDataOcean Infrastructure.
2. **DC-TR-2:** The BDO Data Indexer facilitates the timely and efficient curation of large scale datasets which have been indexed and are thus quickly and efficiently searchable and identifiable.
3. **DS-TR-1:** The BDO Data Indexer facilitates the timely and efficient management of large datasets.

Figure 3-10 displays the execution flow of the BDO Data Indexer.

Figure 3-10: Data Indexer Sequence Diagram

3.2.9 ONTARIO

Ontario is a data management tool that will support the Big Maritime Data sources harmonisation. It will address the following requirements:

4. **DS-TR-4:** Ontario will be able to provide semantification on-the-fly.
5. **DS-TR-1:** The Data Lake is able to store Big Data.
6. **DS-TR-2:** In the Data Lake, data are stored in different formats and are accessed using different native data management engines.
7. **DU-TR-1:** Data in Ontario can be queried efficiently as if they were in the same format and data scheme.

Ontario relies on a Data Lake to store both streamed data generated by sensors, as well as historic, social, scientific, biological, and open data. In the Data Lake, data is ingested in raw formats, e.g., CSV, JSON, or RDF, and is accessed using native data management engines, e.g., SQL or NoSQL engines. Ontario builds a Semantic Layer on top of this Data Lake, which is responsible for mapping data into existing Semantic vocabularies/ontologies, as well as querying these data in their native query languages. Ontario Semantic Layer allows users to deal with heterogeneous data as if it was in one

unique format. Furthermore, Ontario implements data processing techniques that enables query processing and data analytics over data collected from heterogeneous data sources.

During data processing, data is extracted, queried, and analysed using a unique high-level declarative query language, e.g., SPARQL or SQL. In order to provide a unified query processing layer, Ontario implements the following steps:

- **Selection of relevant data sources:** Relevant datasets are selected starting from the generated sub-queries and using the mappings between the data sources and global ontology, i.e., rules that map data sources and the BigDataOcean ontologies and vocabularies.
- **Query analysis and decomposition:** The query is decomposed into sub-queries. An execution plan is generated. Ontario query decomposition and planning techniques are tuned to identify query execution plans that minimise execution time.
- **Query execution:** The sub-queries are translated into queries against the native engines of the selected sources. These queries are executed against the native engines.
- **Query planning and result conciliation:** The answers produced by the sub-queries are merged to produce the query answer according to the corresponding query plan.

Figure 3-11: ONTARIO Architecture

The main characteristics of Ontario are that the query execution process does not require any data materialisation or shipping, and is fully transparent to the user. Data extraction rather happens fully on-the-fly upon queries are posed on the Ontario query interface.

Figure 3-12: ONTARIO Sequence Diagram

3.2.10 Query Builder

The Query Builder is the component responsible for allowing its users to explore, combine and express complex queries on BigDataOcean datasets. The user interface's ease of use ensures that end users unfamiliar with formal query languages or the structure of the underlying data will still be able to describe complex queries on top of multiple datasets. The produced queries will then be used in order to retrieve raw data from BigDataOcean or passed onto other tools, such as the Visualiser, Algorithms Customiser and the Algorithms Combiner. The Query Builder will also ensure that the generated queries will be used to provide data without any violation of data access policies defined within the platform.

The Query Builder will address the following requirement:

1. **DU-TR-1:** Query Builder will allow end users to perform simple and advanced queries over the stored big data.

The purpose of the Query Builder is to be simple to use, yet powerful enough in order to be able to describe the vast majority of queries that can be expected. The tool's strength will be the use of metadata provided by Metadata Repository in order to better predict the needs and intentions of users, help them with most common tasks and provide better insights in the domain of interlinking data from distinct datasets.

The execution flow of the Query Builder can be broken into the following parts, and an example is used to better demonstrate the proposed workflow:

- The user can open a dataset (to which they have access) and explore all of the data variables defined in that dataset (*for example, the user opens the Wave Forecast Database*).
- After that, they can select one or more variables and add them to the “Workbench” area, effectively adding them to the query (*in the example, the user picks the wave height variable and drags it into the Workbench*).
- The selected variables can be filtered or prioritised based on different attributes of the variable (*for example, in the added wave height variable the user applies a chronological filter for a specific period on the time attribute and then orders the result from the largest to the smallest variable values*).
- The selected variables can also be graphically linked to other variables (*in the example mentioned above, the user can link the Wave height’s location with the Depth variable from the Oceanographic database to include that information in their query*).
- Finally, the user can perform some query-level configuration and execute the query to get the requested results (*for example, they may limit the number of results to 100 per day, view a visualisation of the results and download the generated dataset*).

A diagrammatic representation of the workflow described above is provided in the figure below:

Figure 3-13: Query Builder Sequence Diagram

3.2.11 Algorithms Controller

The Algorithms Controller is the component responsible for initiating and monitoring the execution of the requested algorithm. This component is acting as the supervisor of the algorithm execution for the data analysis. The role of this component is very crucial for addressing the stakeholder’s needs.

Algorithms Controller should be able to perform advanced analytics over multiple datasets that are available on the Big Data Storage with a wide range of algorithms and provide results in a timely and efficient manner.

The algorithms controller addresses the following requirements:

1. **DAN-TR-1:** The algorithms controller facilitates the performance of big data analytic algorithms on the data stored / linked in the BigDataOcean platform including descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics.
2. **DAN-TR-2:** The algorithms controller facilitates the storage of results of the analyses as datasets that can be further analysed with other algorithms.
3. **DAN-TR-3:** The algorithms controller is performed on a scalable cluster-computing framework, programming entire clusters with implicit data parallelism and fault-tolerance.
4. **DAN-TR-4:** The algorithms controller has the capability to perform streaming analytics.

The execution flow will be broken down to several parts, each one realising one step of the complete execution. At first it will offer the list of available datasets for selection. Since it is critical that the Algorithms Controller will have the ability to support analysis spanning across multiple datasets the user will be able to select multiple datasets. Once the valuable datasets have been selected, then a list of the data analysis algorithms will be presented for selection. It is highly important that the Algorithms Controller will provide a wide list of big-data enabled analysis algorithms with predefined default parameters values. Depending on the selected algorithm, the Algorithms Controller might receive input from the Algorithms Customiser which is responsible for providing the initial parameter values if the algorithm supports it. The Algorithms Controller will utilise this input to initialise the algorithm execution, giving the option to users to customise the algorithm.

Upon selecting the desirable datasets and algorithm with the appropriate parameters, the core functionality of this component is utilised. A request for the data analysis of the selected datasets initiated to Spark which is the underlying clustering computing framework. The request can be also scheduled by the user for future execution besides immediate execution. The Algorithms Controller is responsible to monitor the execution of this request and to provide the results to the Visualiser component which will provide the advanced visualisations of the results.

Figure 3-14 displays the execution flow of the Algorithm Controller.

Figure 3-14: Algorithm Controller Sequence Diagram

3.2.12 Algorithms Customiser

The Algorithms Customiser is a supplementary component of the Algorithms Controller that is responsible for providing the parameter values of the algorithm selected by the user, provided that the algorithm requires parameters. The role of Algorithms Customiser is very concrete and crucial as it will provide the capability of customising the algorithm's parameters thus the ability of personalising the algorithm upon the user's needs towards the extraction of valuable results and analysis.

The core functionality of this component will be to initially provide a set of default values for the parameters of the algorithm. Following the suggestion of the default values the user will be able to customise the parameter values according to the needs of the user's analysis. Furthermore, it shall be possible for the user to save the parameter values used for later reference or reuse.

The Algorithms Customiser addresses the following requirements:

1. **DAN-TR-1:** The Algorithms Customiser facilitates the customisation of big data analytic algorithms to be performed on the data stored / linked in the BigDataOcean platform.
2. **DAN-TR-4:** The Algorithms Customiser has the capability to customise algorithms supporting streaming analytics.

Figure 3-15 displays the execution flow of the Algorithm Customiser.

Figure 3-15: Algorithms Customiser Sequence Diagram

3.2.13 Algorithms Combiner

The Algorithms Combiner is another supplementary component of the Algorithms Controller that is offering the capability of executing algorithms in a chainable way. This will add further value on the BigDataOcean platform as it extends the analysis that can be performed.

More specific, the Algorithms Combiner will provide the mechanism to accomplish further analysis by executing a selected algorithm on the results of the execution of a previous selected algorithm, thus creating a chain of algorithms execution. Once the results of the selected algorithm are ready the Algorithms Combiner will present the option to execute a new algorithm over the produced results.

The Algorithms Combiner addresses the following requirements:

1. **DAN-TR-1:** The Algorithms Combiner facilitates the performance of big data analytic algorithms on the data stored / linked in the BigDataOcean platform including descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics.
2. **DAN-TR-2:** The Algorithms Combiner facilitates the storage of results of the analyses as datasets that can be further analysed with other algorithms.
3. **DAN-TR-3:** The Algorithms Combiner is performed on a scalable cluster-computing framework, programming entire clusters with implicit data parallelism and fault-tolerance.
4. **DAN-TR-4:** The Algorithms Combiner has the capability to perform streaming analytics.

The following figure displays the execution flow of the Algorithm Combiner.

Figure 3-16: Algorithms Combiner Sequence Diagram

3.2.14 Visualiser

The Visualiser is the component responsible for the visual representation of the results produced from the other components. It addresses the following requirements:

1. **DU-TR-2:** Visualiser is able to visualize stored and real-time data using common chart types (bar chart, line chart, pie chart, etc.).
2. **DU-TR-3:** Visualiser refers to user-defined queries in order to access the underlying data.
3. **DU-TR-4:** Various data such as data aggregations, real-time data and spatial datasets can be fed into the Visualiser.
4. **DU-TR-5:** Visualiser facilitates the creation of static and dynamic dashboards and reports.
5. **DU-TR-6:** Visualiser allows users to export data and results of visualisations through APIs.

Computer-based visualisation systems provide visual representations of datasets designed to help people carry out tasks more effectively. Particularly this component will offer a variety of visual representations including bar and scatter plots, pie charts, heat maps, etc. based on the execution output of queries composed by the Query Builder component. It will also display the analysis results executed by the Algorithm Controller component. The visualisations will be provided within various contexts within the BigDataOcean platform, including:

- The Query Builder in order to allow users to generate visualisations of the explored data.
- Analytics will use the Visualiser to provide insights into the results of the executed analysis.
- Reports and dashboards will include results of the Visualiser in order to become more interactive and intuitive for the end user.

- The results of this component will be also available for export as static images or embeddable assets.

The execution flow is broken down to three parts, following the what/why/how visualisation analysis framework¹ that first defines what data will be represented, then the main purposes of the representation (why) and finally how the visual encoding and interaction idioms are constructed in terms of design choices.

The “What” defines the dataset structure and the data types. Tabular data and structured documents are the most fundamental structures. Other possible structures are also sets, lists and clusters. Each dataset structure comprises a set of various data type combinations of items, links, attributes, positions and grids which are the five possible data types. Dataset may be updated continuously and thus presented dynamically after gradually processing the data as stream, or in the form of a static file.

It is important though, to understand the actions that user will perform upon the visualisation. In some cases, the user may be interested to share some representation of data or data. They may wish to highlight outliers, browse data with specific attribute constraints or visually showcase trends and other changes. Furthermore, the user may also wish to access data from different aspects and with variable levels of granularity and accuracy – in essence, to *drill into data*. All these cases summarise the “Why” aspect of the methodology.

Finally, the third step of the methodology, namely the “How” part, includes the steps needed to construct the visualisation out of a set of design choices. This step comprises the spatial data arrangement, data manipulation, provision of data facets and data reduction such as filtering or aggregation.

The BigDataOcean execution flow will be broken down into several parts,

- At first the Visualiser component will receive from other components, such as the Query Builder or the Algorithm Controller data to be visualised.
- Based on the dataset types, availability and other available metadata, the user will be prompted to select the target visualisation type. The system will also make a guess about the most appropriate type, in order to minimise the need for user input in many common cases.
- Upon selecting the actions and the target visualisation, based also on the type and the availability of the dataset, the third part of the methodology which will identify the set of specific design choices that fulfil the user goals and the visualisation targets is executed. The outcome of this step is the visual representation of the dataset.

Figure 3-17 displays the execution flow of the Visualiser.

¹ MUNZNER T.: Visualization Analysis and Design. CRC Press, 2014. 1, 2

Figure 3-17: Visualiser Sequence Diagram

3.2.15 Integrated Security Design

BigDataOcean will implement an integrated security design which will be spread along the whole platform and will not be an autonomous and separate component. Following this approach, for all the designed components and the described workflows security mechanisms and protocols will be used towards a high-level of security platform. Taking this approach into consideration every component will be implemented with the appropriate security functionalities in mind. This includes security of data in storage, in transit and in use.

The Integrated Security Design addresses the following requirement:

1. **DS-TR-6:** The Integrated Security Design offers native security and encryption mechanisms.

One of the aspects of integrated security design addresses security of data in storage. Data in storage is referring to any data stored within the BigDataOcean platform, particularly any datasets and metadata stored on the Big Data Storage. Within this aspect for any data stored physically in any digital form on the platform data security, privacy and integrity of data will be taken into consideration. For the Big Data Storage component, it is crucial that the offered security mechanisms of the storage solution are evaluated and configured in a proper way that will comply with the mentioned characteristics. The project technical partners have identified a number of candidate technologies for securing data at storage including Symmetric Encryption Algorithms, Asymmetric Encryption algorithms as well as Attribute-Based Encryption.

The second aspect of integrated security design addresses security of data in transit. Data in transit is referring to any data that are being transferred over the internal network of Big Data Ocean or outside the internal network, for example over the internet or from a local drive to the Big Data Storage. This is a very crucial aspect given the fact that cyber-attacks and cyber-sniffing is very common in our days

and in general data in transit are considered the most vulnerable data. For these purposes security mechanisms like IPsec and TLS which are two of the most valuable mechanisms to address these concerns are under consideration by the consortium.

The third aspect of integrated security design addresses security of data in use. Data in use is referring to any data currently stored locally on any node of the system mainly for internal use like in resident memory, or swap, or processor cache or disk cache. These data can be regarded as "secure" if and only if (a) access to the memory is rigorously controlled, and (b) regardless of how the process terminates (either by successful completion, or killing of the process, or shutdown of the computer), the data cannot be retrieved from any location other than the original at rest state, requiring re-authorisation. For BigDataOcean to address the data in use security requirements, the security mechanisms of Homomorphic Encryption and Verifiable Computation will be considered. Homomorphic Encryption allows the chaining together of different services without exposing the data to each of those services. Verifiable Computation enables a computer to offload the computation of some function, to other perhaps untrusted clients, while maintaining verifiable results. Both mechanisms offer security with privacy preservation for data of increased importance when critical data is in use by different components providing the quarantine of security of the data.

4 Conclusions

The scope of D4.2 was to document the preliminary efforts undertaken within the context of Tasks T4.3 – Components' and APIs' Definition and Design, and T4.4 – BigDataOcean Scalable Architecture Design. Towards this end, the scope of the current deliverable was twofold: On the one hand, it aimed at defining and documenting the main components that need to be integrated in the BigDataOcean platform. In this context, the technical requirements documented in D4.1 were analysed, and a set of concrete components with distinct characteristics and functionalities, addressing properly all identified requirements were defined. In total, a set of 15 components was defined, each one capable of performing a specific set of actions / functionalities and addressing a specific set of requirements. On the other hand, D.4.2 aimed at integrating all identified components into a logical diagram facilitating a complete information flow, comprising the preliminary version of the conceptual architecture of the integrated platform. The architecture will be designed in a modular way facilitating easy maintenance, modifiability and extensibility, and can thus be used and easily extended and customised accordingly in order to include further stakeholder's needs not considered until now, including new inputs to reach different needs of current stakeholders, as well as new stakeholders.

The design of the BigDataOcean platform architecture is a living process that will last until M26. Thus, D4.2 constitutes a living document, with updates based upon further identified functional requirements translated into technical requirements, stemming mainly from feedback received by the project's pilots being merged into future versions of this deliverable, updating and customising or even modifying the architecture accordingly. The future versions of D4.2, apart from integrating additional identified functional, non-functional and technical requirements and translating them into software components addressing them, will also include the actual technical architecture of the BigDataOcean platform, diving into the implementation details of each software component, and the description of the technical interfaces between the platform's components, facilitating their interconnection.

Annex I: Mapping Requirements to Components

Code	Technology Requirement	Priority	Components Responsible
DAC-TR-1	The system should be able to connect and acquire data from sensors and IoT devices of different manufactures in real-time or intervals.	Medium	Tupler, Big Data Framework & Storage
DAC-TR-2	The system should be able to obtain data from AIS receivers, transponders or base stations.	High	Tupler, Big Data Framework & Storage
DAC-TR-3	The system should be able to acquire data from large and popular oceanographic databases including Copernicus through APIs.	High	Tupler, Big Data Framework & Storage
DAC-TR-4	The system should be able to upload big data datasets on BigDataOcean infrastructure.	High	Tupler, Big Data Framework & Storage
DAC-TR-5	The system should be able to link big data sources to BigDataOcean Infrastructure.	High	Annotator / Mapper, RDF Metadata Transformation Engine, Data Indexer
DAN-TR-1	The system should be able to perform big data analytic algorithms on the data stored / linked in the BigDataOcean platform including descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics.	High	Algorithms Controller, Algorithms Customiser, Algorithms Combiner
DAN-TR-2	The system should be able to save results of the analyses as datasets that can be further analysed with other algorithms.	High	Algorithms Controller, Algorithms Combiner
DAN-TR-3	The data analysis framework should be performed on a scalable cluster-computing framework, programming entire clusters with implicit data parallelism and fault-tolerance.	High	Big Data Framework & Storage, Algorithms Controller, Algorithms Combiner
DAN-TR-4	The BDO analytics should have the capability to perform streaming analytics.	Medium	Algorithms Controller, Algorithms Customiser, Algorithms Combiner
DC-TR-1	The system should be able to cleanse the datasets (e.g. remove duplicates, inconsistent values, identify outliers, values with wrong types).	Medium	Cleanser

DC-TR-2	The system should be able to curate large scale (big data) datasets in a timely and efficient manner.	Medium	Big Data Framework & Storage, Data Indexer
DC-TR-3	The system should be able to store the processes followed for the data curation.	Medium	Cleanser, Annotator / Mapper, RDF Metadata Transformation Engine
DC-TR-4	The system should allow for efficient transformation of data: converting values to other formats, normalising and de-normalising.	Medium	Metadata Repository
DC-TR-5	The system should be able to program the semantic curation / reconciliation of datasets.	Medium	Metadata Repository, Annotator / Mapper, RDF Metadata Transformation Engine
DC-TR-6	The data curation tools can be used offline at the client side.	Medium	Annotator / Mapper, RDF Metadata Transformation Engine, Cleanser
DS-TR-1	The system should be able to store and manage large datasets (big data).	High	ONTARIO, Big Data Framework & Storage, Data Indexer
DS-TR-2	Setup of different data storage environments should be allowed in parallel in order to accommodate different storage needs (Relational Databases, NoSQL, TripleStores).	High	ONTARIO, Big Data Framework & Storage
DS-TR-3	The system should have high degree of scalability.	High	Big Data Framework & Storage
DS-TR-4	The system should allow for replication and high availability with no single point of failure.	High	ONTARIO, Big Data Framework & Storage
DS-TR-5	The system should support distributed storage and auto-sharing.	Medium	Big Data Framework & Storage
DS-TR-6	The system should offer native security and encryption mechanisms.	High	Integrated Security Design
DS-TR-7	The system should have a direct pipeline with the chosen cluster computing framework and analytics engine.	Medium	Big Data Framework & Storage
DU-TR-1	The system should be able to perform simple and advanced queries over the stored big data.	High	ONTARIO, Query Builder

DU-TR-2	The system should be able to visualise stored and real-time data using common chart types (bar chart, line chart, pie chart, etc.).	High	Visualiser
DU-TR-3	The visualisations should be linked to the queries performed over the data.	High	Visualiser
DU-TR-4	The system should be able to visualise statistics, real-time data and spatial datasets.	High	Visualiser
DU-TR-5	The system should be able to create and save static and dynamic dashboards and reports.	High	Visualiser
DU-TR-6	The system should be able to export data and results of visualisations through APIs.	High	Visualiser

Annex II: Mapping Components to Requirements

Component	Requirement Code	Requirement Description
Anonymiser	N/A	The Anonymiser currently does not address any specific technical requirements, nevertheless it has been included as an optional component because such a need may arise in the future for the provision of a service through the platform.
	DC-TR-1	The system should be able to cleanse the datasets (e.g. remove duplicates, inconsistent values, identify outliers, values with wrong types).
Cleanser	DC-TR-3	The system should be able to store the processes followed for the data curation.
	DC-TR-6	The data curation tools can be used offline at the client side.
Tupler	DAC-TR-1	The system should be able to connect and acquire data from sensors and IoT devices of different manufactures in real-time or intervals.
	DAC-TR-2	The system should be able to obtain data from AIS receivers, transponders or base stations.
	DAC-TR-3	The system should be able to acquire data from large and popular oceanographic databases including Copernicus through APIs.
	DAC-TR-4	The system should be able to upload big data datasets on BigDataOcean infrastructure.
Metadata Repository	DC-TR-4	The system should allow for efficient transformation of data: converting values to other formats, normalising and de-normalising.
	DC-TR-5	The system should be able to program the semantic curation / reconciliation of datasets.
Annotator / Mapper	DAC-TR-5	The system should be able to link big data sources to BigDataOcean Infrastructure.
	DC-TR-3	The system should be able to store the processes followed for the data curation.
	DC-TR-5	The system should be able to program the semantic curation / reconciliation of datasets.

RDF Metadata Transformation Engine	DC-TR-6	The data curation tools can be used offline at the client side.
	DAC-TR-5	The system should be able to link big data sources to BigDataOcean Infrastructure.
	DC-TR-3	The system should be able to store the processes followed for the data curation.
	DC-TR-5	The system should be able to program the semantic curation / reconciliation of datasets.
	DC-TR-6	The data curation tools can be used offline at the client side.
Big Data Framework & Storage	DAC-TR-1	The system should be able to connect and acquire data from sensors and IoT devices of different manufactures in real-time or intervals.
	DAC-TR-2	The system should be able to obtain data from AIS receivers, transponders or base stations.
	DAC-TR-3	The system should be able to acquire data from large and popular oceanographic databases including Copernicus through APIs.
	DAC-TR-4	The system should be able to upload big data datasets on BigDataOcean infrastructure.
	DAN-TR-3	The data analysis framework should be performed on a scalable cluster-computing framework, programming entire clusters with implicit data parallelism and fault-tolerance.
	DC-TR-2	The system should be able to curate large scale (big data) datasets in a timely and efficient manner.
	DS-TR-1	The system should be able to store and manage large datasets (big data).
	DS-TR-2	Setup of different data storage environments should be allowed in parallel in order to accommodate different storage needs (Relational Databases, NoSQL, TripleStores).
	DS-TR-3	The system should have high degree of scalability.
	DS-TR-4	The system should allow for replication and high availability with no single point of failure.
DS-TR-5	The system should support distributed storage and auto-sharing.	

	DS-TR-7	The system should have a direct pipeline with the chosen cluster computing framework and analytics engine.
Data Indexer	DAC-TR-5	The system should be able to link big data sources to BigDataOcean Infrastructure.
	DC-TR-2	The system should be able to curate large scale (big data) datasets in a timely and efficient manner.
	DS-TR-1	The system should be able to store and manage large datasets (big data).
ONTARIO	DS-TR-1	The system should be able to store and manage large datasets (big data).
	DS-TR-2	Setup of different data storage environments should be allowed in parallel in order to accommodate different storage needs (Relational Databases, NoSQL, TripleStores).
	DS-TR-4	The system should allow for replication and high availability with no single point of failure.
	DU-TR-1	The system should be able to perform simple and advanced queries over the stored big data.
Query Builder	DU-TR-1	The system should be able to perform simple and advanced queries over the stored big data.
Algorithms Controller	DAN-TR-1	The system should be able to perform big data analytic algorithms on the data stored / linked in the BigDataOcean platform including descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics.
	DAN-TR-2	The system should be able to save results of the analyses as datasets that can be further analysed with other algorithms.
	DAN-TR-3	The data analysis framework should be performed on a scalable cluster-computing framework, programming entire clusters with implicit data parallelism and fault-tolerance.
	DAN-TR-4	The BDO analytics should have the capability to perform streaming analytics.
Algorithms Customiser	DAN-TR-1	The system should be able to perform big data analytic algorithms on the data stored / linked in the BigDataOcean platform including descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics.

	DAN-TR-4	The BDO analytics should have the capability to perform streaming analytics.
Algorithms Combiner	DAN-TR-1	The system should be able to perform big data analytic algorithms on the data stored / linked in the BigDataOcean platform including descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics.
	DAN-TR-2	The system should be able to save results of the analyses as datasets that can be further analysed with other algorithms.
	DAN-TR-3	The data analysis framework should be performed on a scalable cluster-computing framework, programming entire clusters with implicit data parallelism and fault-tolerance.
	DAN-TR-4	The BDO analytics should have the capability to perform streaming analytics.
Visualiser	DU-TR-2	The system should be able to visualise stored and real-time data using common chart types (bar chart, line chart, pie chart, etc.).
	DU-TR-3	The visualisations should be linked to the queries performed over the data.
	DU-TR-4	The system should be able to visualise statistics, real-time data and spatial datasets.
	DU-TR-5	The system should be able to create and save static and dynamic dashboards and reports.
	DU-TR-6	The system should be able to export data and results of visualisations through APIs.
	Integrated Security Design	DS-TR-6